

EARTH SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF ISOTROPIC AND ANISOTROPIC TRANSFORMATIONS AND FILTRATIONS OF GRAVITATIONAL ANOMALIES

Isgandarov E.

Associate professor,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Huseynov N.

Master student,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Imanov K.

Master student,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Abstract

This article is devoted to the issue of isotropic and anisotropic transformations and filtration of gravity anomalies. An important stage in the processing and interpretation of gravimetric anomalies is the processing stage, which involves the transformation and filtration of gravity fields to isolate local and regional anomalies from the overall anomalous field. Local gravity anomalies reflect structural heterogeneities in the density properties of rocks, while regional anomalies are associated with the deep structure of the Earth's crust and lithosphere. To perform isotropic and anisotropic transformations of gravimetric anomalies, the department has developed algorithms and the Force-Fortran programs IZOTR and ATPAZ, which enable computer-based transformations of analog and digital data using various conversion methods. The article describes the algorithm of the IZOTR program, the theory of the anisotropic palette of the ATRAZ program, as well as some results of the transformation of actual and model gravitational fields in a modern interface, as well as some results of isotropic and anisotropic filtering using the SURFER graphical program.

Keywords: gravity anomaly, gravitational field, filtration, isometric palette, gravity gradients, rectangular palette.

Introduction

Currently, gravity surveys worldwide, including in Azerbaijan, are performed using high-precision digital instruments, which ensures the acquisition of reliable initial data on gravity fields. As is well known, an important stage in the processing and interpretation of gravity data is the primary processing stage, which includes the process of transforming and filtering gravity fields to identify local and regional anomalies and linearly elongated zones of density heterogeneity in rocks. Local anomalies and gradients of gravity fields reflect structural heterogeneities and faults in the sedimentary strata. Regional anomalies and gradients are associated with the deep structure and heterogeneities and fault zones of the earth's crust. To identify local and regional isometric and elongated anomalies of the gravity field, elements of mathematical statistics are used with the use of various algorithms and programs for transforming and filtering data on a computer, and many published works are devoted to this issue [1-5]. For several years, the Department of Geophysics of the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University has been conducting research to increase the resolution of gravity data processing and interpretation. The main goal of this research is to improve conventional methods, algorithms, and programs for data processing and interpretation to

enhance the efficiency of gravity exploration in solving geological and geophysical problems. It should be noted that isotropic and anisotropic field transformations are based on elements of mathematical statistics, while various low-frequency and high-frequency filtering and filtering with multidirectional gradients are based on the frequency representation of gravity anomalies using the Fourier transform [6]. Therefore, the combined use of these types of transformations is advisable for the reliable separation of the gravity field. The main goal in this direction is the development of methods, algorithms, and the selection of optimal parameters for the reliable extraction of useful information.

Means and methods

Transformation is a process by which the observed complex field is divided into its constituent elements. There are various methods of transformation. Transformations used in the areal approach are divided into isotropic and anisotropic. These methods are based on the theory of palettes. In the case of isotropic transformations, a circular or square palette with nodal points, created on a transparent base, is used (Fig. 1). A circular palette can have several internal radii, and a square with several internal squares. The number of

a - circular palette; b - square palette
 Fig. 1. Isotropic transformation palettes

radii (squares) and nodes depends on the nature of the observed field and the measurement accuracy of the instrument. The dimensions of the palettes, in accordance with the scale of the original field map, depend on the depth of the anomaly-forming object being studied. The initial data are the Bouguer gravity anomalies or the magnetic field anomaly.

The area averaging method is a statistical method. It involves calculating the average field value over the circumference of a circular palette at each point in a uniformly quantized field. Typically, this transformation method is performed on a computer using appropriate programs and algorithms. However, these

methods are based on the palette method. To input field values into the computer, the original field is first quantized (discretized) by linear interpolation at the nodes of a square grid, typically 1x1 cm in size at the scale of the original map. Based on the calculation results, a map of regional anomalies and a map of local gravity anomalies are constructed, which serve as the initial data for quantitative interpretation [8].

To perform isotropic transformations of gravity fields, the department developed the IZOTR algorithm and program [7], which enables isotropic transformations of digital and analog data using various transformation methods with arbitrary parameters (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the Force-Fortran program IZOTR

According to the IZOTR algorithm, the following parameters are entered at the beginning:

ZMAC is a map scale factor; LP, LG, LGO are a flag for entering $\Delta g(i, j)$ values in map form, a flag for entering $\Delta g(i, j)$ values by columns, and a flag for entering error values and their coordinates; N, M, FOR, SOCH are a number of rows, columns, format factor,

and interpolation error level; NTR is a three-digit transformation number depending on the transformation method (Saksov-Niagard residual anomalies (gradient method), analytical continuation into the upper and lower half-spaces, transformation by the averaging method with a circular palette, full horizontal gravity gradient, second vertical derivatives of gravity (using

the Elkins formula); NRO, RO, NMD are the number of transformation radii, transformation radius value, map scale reduction factor for printing by NMD times.

The ĪZOTR algorithm includes the following isotropic transformation methods:

1) Area averaging method:

$$\Delta g_{loc} = g(0) - \Delta g_{reg}, \quad (1)$$

Here $\Delta g_{reg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta g(r_i)}{n}$ is an average component of the original field; n is the number of nodal points in the circular palette.

2) Saksov-Nigard gradient method R(g):

$$R(g) = \frac{\Delta g(r_1) - \Delta g(r_2)}{r_2 - r_1} \quad (2)$$

3) Third vertical derivatives of the Elkins gravity potential;

$$\frac{1}{60r^2} [44g(0) + 16\bar{g}(r_1) - 12\bar{g}(r_2) - 48\bar{g}(r_3)], \quad (3)$$

here $g(0)$, $\bar{g}(r_i)$ are the value of gravity in the center of the circular palette and the average (regional) value over a circle with radius r_i .

If the shape of geological structures deviates from isometric, that is, if their direction of occurrence (extent) changes, then the orientation of the stacking palette at each point is important to account for the directionality of local anomalies. In other words, an algorithm must be developed to select the azimuth of the stacking palette. Anisotropic transformations are used to separate linearly oriented local anomalies. These types of transformations relate to averaging and field gradient calculation methods. To perform anisotropic transformations, a rectangular stacking palette is used, the length of which is several times greater than its width (Fig. 3).

For anisotropic transformation, two coordinate systems must be selected. One is fixed, used to determine the coordinates of the observation points of the uniformly quantized field. The other coordinate system is associated with a rotating anisotropic palette and is used to determine the coordinates of the palette nodes at which the initial potential field values are interpolated (Fig. 4). To determine the field values at the nodes of the In order to determine the field values at the nodes of an anisotropic palette, the distance R between the node of the anisotropic palette and the starting point of the square of the quantized field within which this node is located is first calculated using the formula:

Puc. 3. Anisotropic transformation palette

(x_i, y_i) is a coordinates of the field quantization points in the fixed coordinate system;
 (x_0, y_0) - coordinates of the center of the palette in the fixed coordinate system;
 (x'_i, y'_i) - coordinates of the nodal points of the palette in the moving coordinate system;
 (ξ_i, η_i) - coordinates of the nodal points of the palette in the fixed coordinate system;
 $\Delta\alpha$ - counterclockwise rotation angle of the palette axis.
 Fig. 4. Rotating anisotropic transformation palette

$$R = \sqrt{(\xi_i - x_i)^2 + (\eta_i - y_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

If the length R is 0.75 less than the quantization step of the initial field, then a plane is drawn through the vertex of the upper triangle and, based on this, interpolation values are calculated for the main points of the summation palette:

$$G(\xi_i, \eta_i) = (\xi - x_i - 1)[G(x_i + 1, y_i + 1) - G(x_i, y_i + 1)] + (\eta - y_i) * [G(x_i + 1, y_i + 1) - G(x_i + 1, y_i)] + G(x_i + 1, y_i + 1) \quad (6)$$

To interpolate the observation fields at other points of the aggregating palette, it is sufficient to continue the analogous cycle. And then the field values are calculated using the above formulas. In order to determine the maximum values of the intensity of local anomalies, it is necessary to repeat the above interpolation and summation cycle depending on the angle of rotation of the summing vane. For this, the cycle is carried out by changing the angle of rotation of the summing vane at each point of the initial area. However, at small steps of the angle of rotation, the machine calculation time increases sharply.

To perform anisotropic transformations of gravitational fields, the department developed the ATRAZ algorithm and program, which allows for the execution

$$G(\xi_i, \eta_i) = (\xi_i - x_i)[G(x_i + 1, y_i) - G(x_i, y_i)] + (\eta - y_i) * [G(x_i, y_i + 1) - G(x_i, y_i)] + G(x_i, y_i) \quad (5)$$

If R is 0.75 times larger than the quantization step, then the plane passes through the vertex of the lower triangle, from which the interpolation value is calculated:

of anisotropic transformations of digital and analog data on a computer using various conversion methods with arbitrary parameters.

Results and discussion

Below are presented some results of isotropic and anisotropic processing of actual and simulated gravity-magnetic fields using the developed programs, as well as filtering results for identifying local anomalies and gradients of gravity fields in a modern interface. The results of isotropic transformation of the gravity field of the eastern Middle-Kura Depression using the averaging method and the IZOTR program are shown below in 2D format (Fig. 5).

Maxima and minima:

1 is the Nasimkend; 2 is the Saryjalyar; 3 is the Sabirabad; 4 is the Arabkubali; 5 is the Chovranli; 6 is the Jarli; 7 is the Rahimli; 8 is the Kurdamir; 9 is the Alpout; 10 is the Myusly; 11 is the Mugan; 12 is the Varkhan; 13 is the Mollakend; 14 is the Muradkhanli; 15 is the Shakhsuni; 16 is the Ujar; 17 is the Agdash; 18 is the Ashagi-Lyaki; 19 is the Piraza; 20 is the Zardob.

Fig. 5. Results of isotropic transformations of the gravity field by averaging for the eastern part of the Middle Kura Depression (in mGal units)

The transformation was performed to identify large local elements of the gravity field of the detailed gravimetric survey area with an outer radius of 20 km and inner radii of 10 and 15 km. The map of local anomalies Δg_{20} shows large local maxima of varying intensity, such as Saatly-Sabirabat (18 mGal), Zardob (2.5 mGal), Muradkhanli (4 mGal), Myusly and Kurdamir (3 mGal), Rahimli (7 mGal), Chovranli (6 mGal). Analysis of this map and comparison with the

map of local magnetic anomalies confirms that the nature of these maxima is associated with the uplift of igneous rocks, to which uplifts of the Paleogene-Mesozoic complex of deposits are confined.

Of interest are the results of filtering the model gravity field using the capabilities of the world-famous SURFER program (Fig. 6). As can be seen in the figure, the top left shows a model digital map of the original gravity field (Fig. 6a), which is complicated by the presence of local gravity protrusions. The anomaly intensity changes in the direction from

a is a gravity field model; *b* is a result of mid-frequency filtering (local anomaly map); *c* is a result of filtering by the Order-1 Derivation filter method (Roberts Row detector 3x3); *d* is a result of filtering by the Order-1 Derivation filter method (Prewitt Row detector 3x3).

Fig. 6. Results of various filtering methods for the gravitational field model

northwest to southeast (from -3 to +23 mGal). The top right shows a map of local anomalies obtained by filtering using the method we developed [9]. The map shows four maximum and minimum local gravity anomalies of varying intensity (Fig. 6b). The bottom panel shows the filtering results using the Order-1 Derivation filter (Robert Row detector 3x3) (Fig. 6c) and the Order-1 Derivation filter (Previt Row detector 3x3) (Fig. 6d). These maps highlight positive and negative gradient zones associated with the boundaries of local anomalies. Filtering map (d) most clearly characterizes these boundaries. Filtering map (c), in contrast to map (d), displays the reverse signs and directions of the gradients.

Conclusions:

1. Isotropic and anisotropic transformations and filtering of gravity-magnetic data allow us to extract local and regional gravity components from a complex observed field. Anisotropic transformations and filtering allow us to extract local and regional gravity components taking into account the direction and orientation of anomalies. The Force-Fortran algorithm of the IZOTR program, which performs isotropic transformations of gravity-magnetic fields, is described.

2. The issue of anisotropic transformation of gravity-magnetic fields is analyzed. The mathematical foundations of the anisotropic palette developed at the department of the ATRAZ program are shown, which

can rotate around its axis with a certain angular step for operation in the mode of selecting gradient zones.

3. The results of isotropic transformation by the method of averaging the gravitational field of the eastern part of the Middle Kura Depression are analyzed. The gravity field model was filtered using the Order-1 Derivation filter (Roberts Row 3x3 detector) and the Order-1 Derivation filter (Prewitt Row 3x3 detector). The corresponding maps were constructed, on which local anomalies and their corresponding gradient zones were highlighted.

References

1. Amiraslanov T.S. New algorithm for anisotropic transformations of gravitational and magnetic fields. News of Universities: Oil and Gas, 1983, No. 1, pp. 3-7 (In Russian).
2. Iskenderov E.H. Algorithm for effective transformation of gravitational field in the areas with complex composition. GEOPHYSICS NEWS IN AZERBAIJAN, bulletin 2, 1998, p.17-18.
3. Iskandarov E.H. Improvement of efficiency on transformation of gravity anomalies at large depths. Tezis VII Azerbaijan international geophysical conference, Baku-2010., p.116.
4. Iskenderov E.H. Digital processing of gravity-magnetic data. Materials of the Azerbaijan International Geophysics Conference. Geophysics Management Baku, 2017, 1 p.

5. Iskenderov E.H. Digital processing of gravimagnetic data. GEOPHISICS NEWS IN AZERBAIJAN. Geophysics Management. Baku, №1, 2018, pp.37-44 (In Russian).
6. Iskandarov Elkhan Huseyn, You Yunlong You Ligu. Transformation of gravitational anomalies by methods derivatives and gradients. Danish Scientific Journal, № 21, 2019, pp.13-16.
7. Isgandarov Elkhan H. Transformation of gravimagnetic anomalies. Proceedings of the International PARCECO Scientific Conference to be organized by the Azerbaijan-French University (UFAZ) operating under the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, November 30 - December 01, 2021. p. 15.
8. Isgandarov E.H., Kirgizbayev A., Isgandarova L.E. Transformation of gravimagnetic anomalies on the computer. Italy's scientific journal Annali d'Italia, №53, 2024, pp.12-19, pdf, ISSN 3572-2436., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869374>
9. Isgandarov E.H., Zhang Jinbin. Identification of local gravity anomalies by transformation and filtration method. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science, №169, 2025, pp.8-14, ISSN 3453-9875.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17738487>.